

Green Library in the time of ecological Crisis: A Combination polymer approaches

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Abstract:

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) Green Library award to execute the pivotal role of libraries and librarians with specialized professional knowledge in the advancement of sustainability is considered to be the great initiative. A Green library, also known as a sustainable library, is a library built with environmental concerns in mind. Green libraries are a part of the larger green building movement. Libraries, particularly public libraries, are life-long learning centers for people of all ages in local communities. Libraries are not only repositories of knowledge, but are also important information resources for raising awareness about environmental concerns.

Keywords: Green Library, Sustainable Library, Green Librarian

Introduction:

Green Library and Sustainability both the concepts gain popularity in the recent past. To meet the present needs but securing the fulfilment of future needs of our future generation can be conceptualised as sustainability. Everything is changing rapidly towards the development with help of modern and upgraded technology. With the advancement in every sphere one important thing human civilization just forgot about sustainability. The term 'sustainability' explained by Oxford English, 2008 "forms of human economic activity and culture that do not lead to environmental degradation, esp. avoiding the long-term depletion of natural resources". And in present scenario we need to really devote ourselves to promote the awareness about sustainability and Library is not an exception being a community centre.

The Green Library concept emerged in 1990 and by 2003 the concept got popularity. According to New World Encyclopedia (2017) "A Green library, also known as a sustainable library, is a library built with environmental concerns in mind. Green libraries are a part of the larger green building movement. Libraries, particularly public libraries, are life-long learning centers for people of all ages in local communities. Libraries are not only repositories of knowledge, but are also important information resources for raising awareness about environmental concerns. Green libraries educate the public about environmental issues through their collections, sustainable and environmentally friendly facilities, and public library programs. Among other things, green libraries maximize the effects of natural sun light and natural air flow; green libraries are thoughtfully designed while taking into account site selection to structural design, energy use, materials used and human health effects." The phrase Green or sustainable library used for the building which is designed, construct, refurbished, operated

environmental friendly manner to balance the ecological factor. So it can be said that Green Library may help in improving the library service in sustainable way and along with their services it may help in spreading awareness about sustainable development among the community members.

Factors to be considered in Greening the Library

● **Location:**

As Library is a heart of any institution or university or any department, it should be in a perfect locality such as away from the noise zone like club, auditorium, entertainment hall etc. to make patron concentrate on their study. Also public transportation system to reach library is a necessary element which should need extra attention while choosing location. There are various guidelines have been given by different agency and organizations like Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) and U.S. Green Building Council to develop world class green library

● **Air:**

Proper air circulation is another important factor to be considered to build green library to keep library cool. An effective air circulation needs proper plantation for clean and pure air which restrict usage of air conditioner and cooler. Plantation of the air ventilator plants reduces the electricity consumption and helps in greening the library.

● **Light:**

A green library must possess sufficient number of windows, glass windows and skylights which helps in insertion of natural light uninterruptedly inside the library reading room and there would be no requirement of any electricity generated light during day time. Usage of low energy consuming bulbs and lights in less light areas helps in saving electricity and money as a whole.

- **Water:**

Deterioration of natural resources including water is a big problem and every human being must take the responsibility to save water. Reuse of wastewater, rainwater in toilets or plantation is another important factor towards greening the library.

- **Building Constructional Material:**

Material to construct green library building is another important thing. There are lots of standards and protocols to make a green library building by using recyclable and environment friendly materials.

- **Electricity:**

Restricted use of electricity can be implemented. Other than restriction of consumption of excess electricity solar panel system can be implemented on the rooftop of library building . Not only generation of electricity surplus energy can be conserved for the use of crisis period.

Other than these above mentioned factors some other factors are to be considered which are:

- Putting off power button in idle time or while closing the library.
- Use of recycled paper.
- Utilization of re-usable mugs/beverage containers rather than disposable
- Use of stairs rather than elevators
- Use of duplex and power saving printer along with recyclable toner cartridges
- Construction of a “green team” to monitor the measures taken for greening the library are following correctly
- Announcement of “green” prize to staff member who correctly followed the rules in maintaining sustainable practice inside the library.
- For greening the library patron’s help in gathering funds can also be considered as an important factor.
- To ensure sustainability libraries can organize strategic thinking and planning sessions between staff and patrons and other well wishers of the library.

- **Role of Green Librarian:**

Being a responsible contributor to community learning efforts, a librarian usually takes a leadership role in sustainability movement (Miller, 2010). A librarian rather Green Librarian plays an important role in greening the library. Their role in this regard has been described below:

- The green librarian or eco-librarian must handle the budgets to support the organizations to maintain sustainability.
- They must take the charge of establishment and distribution of information through bringing out the best practices and introducing them to wider use.
- They must motivate people to participate in

the due course of sustainable development by providing environmental guide and work methods.

- Introduction of indicators and monitoring methods for sustainable libraries.
- Green librarian must support individual employee to implement sustainability through commitment i.e. encouragement of sustainability internally.
- Green librarian must provide environmental training, tips for best practices and instructions on how to measure success and encouragement.
- He/she must promote green library tools, techniques to encourage his/her staff and user as well.
- Green librarian must ensure the organization of library resources that are related towards a helpful future for the user in a helpful manner for easy access.
- One of the most important role a Green librarian and his/her associates can play is effective and attentive customer communication as libraries have significant possibilities to meliorate the environmental awareness of their customer through communication and environmental education as well as acting as an example.
- Green librarian must play a pivotal role in promoting social sustainability through higher ground ecological library activities the important role of library in sustainable development should be emphasized more by the Green librarian.
- Green librarian must keep in mind essentially the three important things such as “Economy, Ecology and Equity” to make flourishing, prosperous, healthy, carbon neutral and sustainable libraries.
- Green librarian must ensure the eco-library system and encourage his/her staff to work in this environment.
- An effective regular initiative to promote green library movements by using different online tools like social media has to be taken by the Green librarian. .
- Green librarian may encourage other librarian through discussion, seminar, and conferences by sharing his/her practices.
- Green librarian must promote use of biodegradable materials at the library. Use of wool brick instead of burnt brick can be done. For roof solar tiles or panel can be used.
- Recyclable paper insulation is an ultimate alternative to make environment friendly building. At the same time it protects wall from fire and insects.
- Replacement of steel furniture by using

bamboo or wooden furniture in the library can be promoted by the Green librarian.

- Green librarian may opt for terrace garden or rooftop planting.
- Moreover Green librarians must ensure the standardization of the products & equipments which forms the part of library decorum.
- He/she must call for their user to participate in "Go Green Drive".

Initiatives (International and Indian) Towards Greening the Library:

Many International and National initiative has been taken towards greening the library as the part of sustainable development.

International Initiatives:

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) Green Library award to execute the pivotal role of libraries and librarians with specialized professional knowledge in the advancement of sustainability is considered to be the great initiative. The Singapore National Library, 2005 is the greenest library compare to other libraries in the world. Light shelves have been used inside the library which allows the light to filter into the library, without having any unpleasant effects. The launch of "My Tree House" the green children library in 2013 in Singapore mark another initiative towards sustainable development. Presently Green Star System, Australia is another voluntary project of greening the library.

The Children's Museum of Pittsburgh is another example of implementing sustainable techniques to expand and renovate in 2004. Birkbeck Library England set another example of greening library by removing 87% of indoor pollution by recycling, greening, use of cotton bags and turning off technical gadgets. Spanish Peaks Library, Walsenburg, UK implemented geothermal system for heating and cooling, renovated floor with recycled rubber to promote green library. Anythink Brighton, Brighton, USA is considered to be the first carbon neutral green library with the use of photovoltaic energy generation system along with the use of geothermal system for heating and cooling. Blair Library, USA is an another example of green initiative by Public Library with a cistern to catch rainwater for irrigation a membrane roof, cork flooring, recycled content furnishings, waterless urinals low Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) finishes and fabrics etc. Beside these above discussed libraries there are many more who has undertaken the green initiative towards sustainable development.

Indian Initiatives:

The green awareness about Green Library in India is not very popular. Though, it is quite necessary to build the Green Libraries more in number. Few rating system has been generated

namely Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment (GRIHA) by The Energy and Resources Institute (TERI) to check on energy consumption, waste generation, renewable energy adoption etc. Government of India (GOI) has been adapted GRIHA as the national rating system. Centre of Science and Technology for Rural Development (COSTFORD), Kerala and Habitat Technology Group, Kerala helps in building fruitful, energy efficient and more earmarks housing for all groups. There are very few library in India which are going Green. Anna Central Library, Chennai is considered to be the Asia's first LEED Gold rated library building.

The vision of this library is to be internationally recognised for its contribution towards economic vitality, environmental sustainability and quality of life through excellence in learning, research and community engagement. Madras University Library is considered as a green library for its architectural design as it allows to circulate fresh air, prevent direct sunlight and allow the entry of adequate natural lights. NIT, Silchar is another example of green library. The design of new library building has been done following LEED, USA certification system. Perma Karpo Library, Ladakh in Indian Himalayas with ventilated trombe walls, wool insulation, a roof made of mud and timber paneling, solar panels, white lotus garden and usage of innovative technologies promote the practice of sustainable development since 2010. Delhi University Library, Delhi, Karnataka University Library, Dharwad, Mumbai University Library, National Library of India India (Kolkata) is the example of Green Library initiative in India.

Conclusion:

Global warming has a negative effect on planet earth due to severe pollution which includes greenhouse gas, glacier retreat, changes of timing in seasonal events etc. In this respect we human being have some responsibility to call for "Going green" and pay attention in sustainable development. Library being a community centre and as an asset to the future must step up and help in promoting awareness on sustainable development. Libraries always played a pivotal role in educating people to promote awareness and empower them make a difference.

This time library must adopt a strategy to become green and sustainable. Library professionals should encourage various practices of "greening libraries" and focus on decisive and clear headed steps to guarantee future sustainable development of libraries. As libraries continue to take a more progressive stance on improving the human condition, sustainability will have to be a central theme to contribute in green library movement. There are many international and national

initiatives for “Going green” and best practices in the library. Though in India the consciousness about green library is less and it is high time to participate in greening the library and contribute in sustainable development.

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